

Mapping the Emergency Medicine Landscape in Tanzania: A Workforce, pre-hospital, and Health Facility Study, Fifteen Years Post-Introduction (2010-2025)

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Ethical approval: Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences Research and Ethics Committee (Ref. No. DA.282/298/01.C/3175)

ABSTRACT

Background: Emergency Medicine (EM) has rapidly evolved as a critical specialty in Tanzania since its formal introduction in 2010, including establishment of the country's first EM training program at Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences (MUHAS), development of emergency departments (EDs) at tertiary hospitals, and formation of the Emergency Medicine Association of Tanzania (EMAT). However, fifteen years on, no national-level documentation exists detailing the number, training background, geographic distribution, and roles of EM physicians, nor a mapped inventory of functioning EDs across health system levels. Understanding this alignment is essential for workforce planning, infrastructure investment, and equitable emergency care delivery.

Objective/Aim: To assess the national landscape of Emergency Medicine in Tanzania 15 years after its inception, focusing on prehospital care, distribution of EM-trained physicians, and availability of functioning emergency departments across the healthcare system.

Material and Methods: This is a cross-sectional, descriptive, geospatial study using complete enumeration of all known EM physicians in Tanzania as of 2025. Data sources include MUHAS alumni records, EMAT, the Medical Council of Tanganyika (MCT), the Medical Association of Tanzania (MAT), and the Ministry of Health (MOH). ED data will be obtained from the Ministry's Emergency Services Unit, EMAT, and hospital registries. Physicians will be classified by training origin (local vs. international), current location (in-country vs. diaspora), and role (clinical, non-clinical, or mixed). GIS mapping and statistical analyses will assess distribution, service burden, and spatial clustering. Analyses will be conducted in R (v4.5.2), Microsoft Excel™ 2021, and GIS analyses in QGIS v3.44.3.

Expected Outcomes: A comprehensive national dataset on EM workforce and facility capacity to inform policy, training programs, strategic deployment, and health system strengthening.

Keywords: Emergency medicine, Tanzania, Health workforce, Health facilities, Low- and middle-income countries, Health system mapping, Human resources.

INTRODUCTION

Emergency Medicine (EM) is a rapidly evolving specialty globally, recognized for its crucial role in reducing morbidity and mortality from acute illnesses and injuries. [1–3] EM addresses the need for timely, coordinated care for undifferentiated patients presenting with life-threatening conditions. It integrates clinical expertise, system organization, and emergency medical services (pre-hospital and facility-based) to ensure rapid assessment, stabilization, and referral.

In many low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), including those in sub-Saharan Africa, EM has gained prominence over the past two decades as governments strive to enhance health system readiness, responsiveness, and resilience.[4–7] Factors such as rapid population growth, increasing urbanization, trauma burden, rising multimorbidity, and frequent disease outbreaks have amplified the demand for high-quality emergency care. Despite its growing importance, emergency care systems in numerous LMICs remain fragmented, under-resourced, and insufficiently staffed.[8,9] Access to timely emergency services is particularly limited in rural areas, where distance, infrastructural deficiencies, and shortages of skilled providers pose significant barriers.[8,10]

Tanzania formally established Emergency Medicine in 2010, marked by the creation of its first emergency department (ED) at Muhimbili National Hospital (MNH) and the initiation of the Emergency Medicine Residency Programme at Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences (MUHAS).[5,7,11] This marked a major milestone in the country’s efforts to strengthen emergency care. Since then, notable progress has included expansion of EM training programs, increased numbers of emergency physicians, improvements in trauma care systems, and the development of emergency units across various regions in the country. However, these advancements have been uneven, and comprehensive documentation remains limited. Pioneering work by *Reynolds et al.* and *Brett et al.* documented this early development of Tanzania’s emergency care system, including the formation of the Emergency Medicine Association of Tanzania (EMAT), a non-profit organization dedicated to advancing EM in the country.[5,7] These foundational efforts laid essential groundwork but also highlighted key gaps, including the concentration of EM specialists in urban tertiary hospitals and the overall shortage of trained personnel.

Fifteen years after EM's inception in Tanzania, there has been considerable expansion in training programs, an increase in emergency medicine professionals, and improvements in health facilities offering emergency care. However, no national-level study has systematically documented the distribution of EM-trained physicians, by training origin, geographic location, and practice role, or provided a comprehensive inventory of functional emergency departments across different levels of the health system (national, zonal, regional, district). Consequently, the alignment between the deployment of emergency medicine workforce and the availability of emergency care infrastructure remains unclear.

This study aims to fill this knowledge gap through a national cross-sectional, geospatial analysis utilizing administrative data from key stakeholder's registry and data base. The primary focus is to map the national emergency medicine landscape, assessing workforce distribution and health facility readiness within the framework of the WHO Health System Strengthening (HSS) model—specifically examining two core building blocks: health workforce (trained EM physicians) and service delivery infrastructure (functional emergency departments across various levels). Additionally, the study adopts frameworks related to health workforce distribution and accessibility. The overarching goal is to generate evidence that informs policy and planning efforts toward achieving equitable and effective emergency care services in Tanzania

This protocol outlines a nationwide mapping study designed to address these critical knowledge gaps, providing essential data to guide strategic investments and strengthen Tanzania's emergency care system.

PROTOCOL

Study design

This will be a cross-sectional, descriptive, geospatial study utilizing administrative and registry data from key Emergency Medicine stakeholders in Tanzania. These include the *Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences (MUHAS)*, the *Medical Council of Tanganyika (MCT)*, the *Emergency Medicine Association of Tanzania (EMAT)*, the *Medical Association of Tanzania (MAT)*, and the *Ministry of Health (MOH)*. The study aims to assess the availability and geographic distribution of Emergency Medicine Physicians (EMPs) and functioning Emergency Medicine departments in Tanzania as of 2025. The STROBE guidelines [12] will be followed when reporting study results.

Study Area

The study will be conducted in Tanzania, a lower-middle-income, East African country with a population of approximately 69 million people as of 2023. [13,14] Geographically and culturally diverse, the country spans over 1,000 kilometres and includes coastal, central plateau, and highland regions. Tanzania has a per capita GDP of USD 1,149. Tanzania has a total number of 11,805 health facilities, comprising 9,366 major facilities which provide comprehensive preventive and curative services (436 Hospitals, 1,126 Health Centres and 7,804 dispensaries) as of 2023. [15] Mainland Tanzania has 26 regions and 169 districts. The semi-autonomous islands of Zanzibar comprise 350 health facilities across 5 regions and 11 districts.

Sampling strategy

This study will utilize complete enumeration (i.e., a census) of all Emergency Medicine-trained practitioners and those practicing in Tanzania as of 2025. It will also include internationally trained practitioners working within the country. For facility data we will include all health facility with EM departments as per Tanzania health facility registry. [16]

Study Participants

Inclusion Criteria

1. All Emergency Medicine physicians trained/practice in Tanzania or abroad and known to be active as of 2025, regardless of whether they are currently practicing in clinical, non-clinical, or mixed roles
2. All health facilities officially designated as having functioning EM departments

Exclusion criteria

1. Individuals whose Emergency Medicine training cannot be verified through MUHAS, MCT, EMAT, or other official records.
2. Emergency care providers without formal EM training (e.g. Registrars, Interns).
3. Facilities not officially designated as Emergency Medicine departments by the MOH.
4. EM residents who have not yet completed their training/graduated by 2025.

Data Collection Tools

Data will be collected at a single point in time using structured surveys and facility assessments to provide a national overview.

1. EMP Data Collection Tool

Captures demographics (sex, age, year of graduation, country of training), current role (clinical, non-clinical, mixed), facility affiliation, level of service, and geographic region of practice.

2. Facility Data Collection Tool

The facility assessment tool collects: Collects facility name, type, level, location (district, region, rural/urban classification), year of establishment, and availability of essential emergency services and infrastructure.

Data will be collected at a single point in time and cross-verified using multiple sources, including MOH, PORALG, and EMAT registries.

Expected Outcomes

This study aims to generate comprehensive data on emergency medicine (EM) workforce distribution, facility readiness, and emergency care capacity in Tanzania. The anticipated outcomes include:

1. *Demographic and Professional Profile of EMPs*: Distribution by age, years of experience, country of training, year of graduation, practice roles, and geographic distribution.
2. *Facility Readiness and Capacity*: Classification of facilities by type and level, availability of emergency departments and services, rural vs. urban distribution, and infrastructure timelines.
3. *Workforce-to-Facility Alignment*: Mapping EMPs to their practice facilities, identifying regions or facility types with workforce shortages, and highlighting gaps in coverage and readiness.
4. *Policy and Training Data*: Identifying areas requiring additional EM training programs and informing deployment strategies to strengthen the health system.
5. *Service Burden Metric*: Population per functioning ED, serving as a proxy for service pressure.

Data analysis and statistical plan

- *Descriptive Statistics*: EMPs by year of graduation, country of training, role, and practice location; EM department distribution by region and facility level.
- *Geospatial Analysis*: GIS mapping using QGIS v3.44.3 overlay mapping to assess EMP–ED alignment.
- *Inequality Assessment*: Adapted Palma ratio comparing population share in the top 10% highest-burden regions to ED share in the bottom 40% lowest-burden regions to evaluate disparities in service availability.
- *Spatial Clustering*: Global Moran's I and Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) will identify clusters and outliers. Statistical significance: $p < 0.05$ using permutation-based inference.
- *Software*: R v4.5.2 and Microsoft Excel 2021; GIS visualization in QGIS.

- *Subgroup Analyses:* By region, rural/urban classification, and facility level. Physicians outside Tanzania will be described but excluded from geospatial analyses.

Data quality will be cross verified through triangulation from at least two independent sources (MOH registry and PORALG). Spatial accuracy will be validated in collaboration with the MOH's Applied Epidemiology team.

Dissemination

Findings will be compiled into a comprehensive report shared with MUHAS, EMAT, the Ministry of Health (Tanzania and Zanzibar), and other relevant stakeholders. A manuscript will be prepared for peer-reviewed publication. Results will also be disseminated through conferences, stakeholder meetings, and open-access repositories. De-identified datasets will be made publicly available in accordance with local data-sharing policies, under the oversight of the Principal Investigator, Dr. Gimbo Hyuha (ghyuha@gmail.com).

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the MUHAS Research and Ethics Committee. (Ref. No.DA.282/298/01.C/3175). This study involves retrospective analysis of existing records and does not involve patient or participant contact. Physician identifiers will be used solely for internal verification, then de-identified for analysis and reporting. Given the secondary nature of data and minimal risk, a waiver of informed consent was granted. For any self-reported data collected, it will be clearly communicated to participants that physician names are used exclusively for data cleaning and verification. All procedures will adhere to relevant ethical standards and confidentiality protocols.

Study status

Ethical approval was obtained on 28 October 2025. Data collection and analysis are currently underway, with manuscript preparation in progress.

CONCLUSION/DISCUSSION

This study seeks to provide a comprehensive baseline mapping of the emergency medicine (EM) prehospital, workforce and health facilities across Tanzania, fifteen years after the formal introduction of EM as a specialty. By systematically assessing the distribution, capacity, and characteristics of EM professionals and the facilities in which they practice, the study aims to identify critical gaps and opportunities for strengthening the national emergency care system. The findings are expected to inform policymakers, health administrators, and educators, supporting evidence-based strategic planning, resource allocation, and workforce development initiatives to enhance emergency care delivery nationwide.

Several limitations are anticipated. Data completeness and accuracy may be affected by nonresponse or partial responses from EM practitioners and health facilities. In addition, reliance on self-reported information regarding training, experience, and facility capacity may introduce recall bias. The cross-sectional design captures a single point in time and may not fully reflect recent or future changes in workforce distribution, facility readiness, or policy environments. Furthermore, nonresponse bias may occur if heavily burdened or less-resourced practitioners and facilities are less likely to participate, potentially resulting in an overrepresentation of better-resourced or more accessible sites.

To mitigate these limitations, multiple strategies will be implemented. Data collection will employ a combination of communication approaches, including email, telephone contact, in-person visits, and established institutional WhatsApp groups, to maximize participation and response rates. Data collectors will undergo standardized training, and validated data collection tools (available as extended data) will be used to ensure consistency and reliability. Self-reported information will be cross verified using facility records, national health databases, and secondary data sources where available. In addition, triangulation of workforce and facility-level data will be conducted to enhance data robustness. Characteristics of non-responding practitioners and facilities will be documented to assess and account for potential nonresponse bias during analysis.

Despite these limitations, this study represents an important step toward strengthening emergency medicine in Tanzania by generating foundational, nationally relevant data. The results will provide critical evidence to support health system reforms, policy development, and resource prioritization, ultimately contributing to improved access to high-quality emergency care and better health outcomes across the country.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article.

Competing interests

Authors declare no competing interests.

Grant information

This study did not receive any external funding or financial support

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank the MUHAS Research and Ethics Committee and the Ministry of Health, Tanzania (Mainland and Zanzibar) for their support. We also acknowledge colleagues and advisors from the MUHAS Emergency Department and DVC Academic for who provided material and guidance throughout the study. Their cooperation and dedication were essential to the successful implementation of this work.

Extended data

Zenodo: *Health Workforce and Facility Data Collection Tools for the Emergency Medicine Landscape Study in Tanzania*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17919995>. License: CC BY 4.0.

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